

Algorithm and Software Implementation of an Optimization Method

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Abstract:

In this article we present an algorithm, software implementation and some numerical experiments for an optimization method applied to unimodal functions, which depends on a conveniently chosen free parameter. This algorithm contains as a particular case the method of golden section, for a certain choice of the parameter. Numerical results showed that the proposed algorithm leads to finding the optimal solution performing a smaller number of iterations than the golden section method, this fact being also justified from theoretical

point of view.

Keywords: *optimization method, unimodal functions, algorithms and software implementation.*

Mathematics Subject Classification: *65K05, 90-04, 90C26.*

Introduction

Optimization as an important branch of mathematics finds its applicability in many fields such as economics, engineering, science and industry. Optimization is an important tool in the analysis of physical systems and in decision science. A quantitative measure of the performance of the system under study is an objective function, which depends on certain characteristics of the system, called variables or unknowns. This objective function could be profit, time, potential energy, or any measure of a characteristic of that system (Nocedal, 1999).

Numerous optimization algorithms have been developed, which were classified according to the nature of the restrictions and the objective function. Thus, we can talk about continuous and discrete optimization, constrained and unconstrained optimization, global and local optimization, stochastic and deterministic optimization, line search methods, trust-region

methods, conjugate gradient methods, Newton and quasi-Newton methods, linear programming, quadratic programming and many others. The models and algorithms of the optimization problems are complicated enough that a computer is needed to implement these processes (Nocedal, 1999).

Optimization algorithms for unidimensional functions are important because they represent a basic component of all multidimensional optimization methods. The most important methods for one-dimensional problems are: the Fibonacci method, the golden section method, the bisection method, and the Newton method (Brinkhuis, 2005).

This article presents an algorithm and software implementation for an optimization method applied to determine the optimal solution of unimodal functions. The algorithm depends on a free parameter in the range (0.5,1), and for a certain particular value it obtains the method of golden section (Kiefer, 1953; Bertsekas, 2016).

In the numerical experiments, the algorithm demonstrated that the number of iterations performed to obtain the minimum point is lower than in the case of golden section method, for the same tolerance value.

Materials and Methods

In what follows, throughout this article, we consider the optimization problem

$$f(x) \rightarrow \min, \quad x \in [A, B],$$

where $[A, B]$ is an interval of the real axis and $f: [A, B] \rightarrow R$ is the objective function, which is unimodal on $[A, B]$, i.e. possesses a unique local minimum $x^* \in [A, B]$.

Since f is unimodal on $[A, B]$, this assumption implies that f is strictly decreasing in $[A, x^*]$ and is strictly increasing in $[x^*, B]$. Also, this property of f leads to the fact that f is unimodal on every smaller interval $[\alpha, \beta] \subset [A, B]$. We note that unimodal functions do not imply continuity or differentiability.

Because f is unimodal on $[A, B]$ we can construct an iterative general algorithm for approximating the x^* . Let us consider two arbitrary points α, β in (A, B) , with $\alpha < \beta$. We distinguish two cases:

1. if $f(\alpha) < f(\beta)$, then $x^* \in [A, \beta]$ (if we suppose that $x^* \in [\beta, B]$, then $A < \alpha < \beta \leq x^*$ and taking into account that f is strictly decreasing in $[A, x^*]$, it follows that $f(\alpha) > f(\beta)$, which is in contradiction with the hypothesis in case 1);
2. if $f(\alpha) \geq f(\beta)$, then $x^* \in (\alpha, B]$ (if we assume that $x^* \in [A, \alpha]$, then $A \leq x^* \leq \alpha < \beta$ and considering that f is strictly increasing in $[x^*, B]$ we deduce $f(\alpha) < f(\beta)$, which is in contradiction with the hypothesis in case 2).

In this way, we have construct a smaller interval in which the point x^* is located. Thus, in the next iteration, the interval in which we are looking for the point x^* is $[A, \beta]$ if $f(\alpha) < f(\beta)$, respectively $[\alpha, B]$ if $f(\alpha) \geq f(\beta)$. The algorithm continues iteratively until we obtain an

interval whose length is smaller than or equal to a tolerance $\varepsilon = 10^{-p}$, $p \in N^*$. At that moment, any point of the last constructed interval approximates the point x^* with tolerance ε .

We notice that the algorithm is very general because the points within each iteration can be chosen arbitrarily (one smaller than other) and only the values of the function in these points are used (without having to know the derivative of the function, as in other optimization method).

Results and Discussion

The proposed algorithm is a particularization of the general method presented in Section 2. It iteratively constructs a sequence of subintervals $[a_k, b_k]$, $k \geq 1$, included in each other, of decreasing length, which contain the point x^* . More precisely, at iteration $k = 1$ the initial uncertainty interval (in which the point x^* is located) is $[a_1, b_1] = [A, B]$. In general, having constructed the uncertainty interval $[a_k, b_k]$ at iteration $k \geq 1$, the new uncertainty interval $[a_{k+1}, b_{k+1}]$ at iteration $k + 1$ is determined as follows

$$[a_{k+1}, b_{k+1}] = \begin{cases} [a_k, \beta_k], & \text{if } f(\alpha_k) < f(\beta_k) \\ [\alpha_k, b_k], & \text{if } f(\alpha_k) \geq f(\beta_k) \end{cases}$$

where

$$\alpha_k = \theta a_k + (1 - \theta) b_k$$

$$\beta_k = (1 - \theta) a_k + \theta b_k$$

and $\theta \in (\frac{1}{2}, 1)$ is an arbitrary parameter.

Proposition 1. The sequences of points α_k, β_k , $k \geq 1$, have the following properties:

- 1) $\alpha_k, \beta_k \in (a_k, b_k)$, $(\forall) k \geq 1$;
- 2) $\alpha_k < \beta_k$, $(\forall) k \geq 1$.

Proof. Let $k \geq 1$ be an arbitrary number.

1) $\alpha_k, \beta_k \in (a_k, b_k)$ being convex combinations of the points a_k, b_k .

$$2) \quad \beta_k - \alpha_k = (1 - \theta) a_k + \theta b_k - \theta a_k - (1 - \theta) b_k = (1 - 2\theta) a_k + (2\theta - 1) b_k =$$

$= (2\theta - 1)(b_k - a_k) > 0$, hence $\alpha_k < \beta_k$. ■

Proposition 2. The sequence of the uncertainty intervals $[a_k, b_k]$, $k \geq 1$, have the following properties:

- 1) $[a_k, b_k] \supset [a_{k+1}, b_{k+1}]$, $(\forall) k \geq 1$;
- 2) $length([a_k, b_k]) \rightarrow 0$ as $k \rightarrow \infty$;
- 3) $x^* \in [a_k, b_k]$, $(\forall) k \geq 1$.

Proof. The proof follows directly from the construction of the intervals $[a_k, b_k]$, $k \geq 1$, taking into account Proposition 1. ■

Proposition 3. The rate of decrease of length of uncertainty intervals, from the iteration k to iteration $k + 1$, is given by

$$\frac{b_{k+1} - a_{k+1}}{b_k - a_k} = \theta, (\forall) k \geq 1.$$

Proof. Choose $k \geq 1$. We distinguish two cases:

$$n = \begin{cases} 1, & \text{if } B - A \leq \varepsilon \\ \text{the smallest integer which satisfies the inequality } n \geq \frac{\ln \frac{\varepsilon}{B-A}}{\ln \theta} + 1, & \text{if } B - A > \varepsilon \end{cases}$$

Proof. If $B - A \leq \varepsilon$, it is obvious that the number of iterations is $n = 1$.

Let us suppose that $B - A > \varepsilon$. It follows that $\frac{\varepsilon}{B-A} < 1$, so $\ln \frac{\varepsilon}{B-A} < 0$. As $\theta \in (\frac{1}{2}, 1)$, we get $\ln \theta < 0$. Therefore, $\frac{\ln \frac{\varepsilon}{B-A}}{\ln \theta} > 0$, thus $\frac{\ln \frac{\varepsilon}{B-A}}{\ln \theta} + 1 > 1$. Since $B - A > \varepsilon$ we still have to build a new iteration after the first one to reach the stop criteria. Hence $n \geq 2$. From Proposition 3 we have $\frac{b_{k+1} - a_{k+1}}{b_k - a_k} = \theta, (\forall) k \geq 1$. Multiplying these relations for $k = 1, 2, \dots, n - 1$ we get $\frac{b_2 - a_2}{b_1 - a_1} \cdot \frac{b_3 - a_3}{b_2 - a_2} \dots \frac{b_n - a_n}{b_{n-1} - a_{n-1}} = \theta^{n-1}$, thus $b_n - a_n = \theta^{n-1}(B - A)$. Consequently, $length([a_n, b_n]) = b_n - a_n \leq \varepsilon$ if and only if $\theta^{n-1}(B - A) \leq \varepsilon$, which is equivalent to $\theta^{n-1} \leq \frac{\varepsilon}{B-A}$, i.e. $(n - 1)\ln \theta \leq \ln \frac{\varepsilon}{B-A}$, thus

1. If $f(\alpha_k) < f(\beta_k)$, then $[a_{k+1}, b_{k+1}] = [a_k, \beta_k]$, hence

$$\begin{aligned} b_{k+1} - a_{k+1} &= \beta_k - a_k \\ &= (1 - \theta)a_k + \theta b_k - a_k \\ &= -\theta a_k + \theta b_k = \theta(b_k - a_k). \end{aligned}$$

2. If $f(\alpha_k) \geq f(\beta_k)$, then $[a_{k+1}, b_{k+1}] = [\alpha_k, b_k]$, therefore

$$\begin{aligned} b_{k+1} - a_{k+1} &= b_k - \alpha_k \\ &= b_k - \theta a_k - (1 - \theta)b_k \\ &= -\theta a_k + \theta b_k = \theta(b_k - a_k). \end{aligned}$$

Consequently, in both cases we have

$$\frac{b_{k+1} - a_{k+1}}{b_k - a_k} = \theta. \blacksquare$$

Proposition 4. The number of iterations $n \geq 1$, that must be built to reach the first uncertainty interval $[a_n, b_n]$, whose length is smaller than or equal to the tolerance ε , is given by:

$n - 1 \geq \frac{\ln \frac{\varepsilon}{B-A}}{\ln \theta}$, hence $n \geq \frac{\ln \frac{\varepsilon}{B-A}}{\ln \theta} + 1$. In this case, the number of iterations is the smallest integer which satisfies the previous inequality. ■

As we stated in Proposition 4, the stop criteria for the algorithm is reached when the length of the uncertainty interval $[a_n, b_n]$ becomes less than or equal to the tolerance ε , that is $b_n - a_n \leq \varepsilon$. Upon reaching this stop criteria, any point x in the uncertainty interval $[a_n, b_n]$ approximates the minimum point x^* with tolerance ε , because

$$\begin{aligned} |x^* - x| &= length([\min\{x^*, x\}, \max\{x^*, x\}]) \\ &\leq length([a_n, b_n]) = b_n - a_n \\ &\leq \varepsilon. \end{aligned}$$

We agree to take as an approximation of the minimum point the middle of the interval $[a_n, b_n]$, that is $x_{min} = \frac{a_n + b_n}{2}$, and the

minimum approximate value of the function f will be $f_{min} = f(x_{min})$.

The golden section method (Kiefer, 1953; Bertsekas, 2016) can be obtained as a particular case of the previously algorithm considering $\theta = \frac{\sqrt{5}-1}{2} \cong 0.61803398874$ (the golden ratio).

Next, we present the input parameters, the output data and the structured pseudocode for the proposed algorithm.

Input Data

- A, B – the left and right bounds of the real interval on which the objective function is defined;
- $f: [A, B] \rightarrow R$ – the analytical expression of objective function, which is unimodal on the interval $[A, B]$;
- θ – the value of the parameter in the interval $(0.5, 1)$;
- $\varepsilon = 10^{-p}$ ($p \in N^*$) – the tolerance for the computation of the minimum point of function f on the interval $[A, B]$.

Output Data

- x_{min} – the approximation value of the minimum point of function f on the interval $[A, B]$, computed with the tolerance ε ;
- f_{min} – the minimum approximate value of the function f on the interval $[A, B]$;
- k – the number of iterations performed to reach the tolerance ε .

Pseudocode

```

k = 1
a1 = A
b1 = B
α1 = θ * a1 + (1 - θ) * b1
β1 = (1 - θ) * a1 + θ * b1
While (bk - ak > ε) do
    If f(αk) < f(βk) then
        ak+1 = ak

```

```

bk+1 = βk
αk+1 = θ * ak+1 + (1 - θ) * bk+1
βk+1 = (1 - θ) * ak+1 + θ * bk+1

```

else

```

ak+1 = αk
bk+1 = bk
αk+1 = θ * ak+1 + (1 - θ) * bk+1
βk+1 = (1 - θ) * ak+1 + θ * bk+1

```

End If

$k = k + 1$

End While

$x_{min} = \frac{a_k + b_k}{2}$

$f_{min} = f(x_{min})$

Number of iterations performed is the last value of k

To implement the algorithm, we chose the C++ language due to its flexibility and the large number of users. Within the program we have defined 4 functions: the objective function whose minimum point will be determined, the procedure that reads the values of the input parameters, the optimization function that implements the algorithm and the procedure that displays the output data.

Program in C++

```

#include <iostream>
#include <math.h>
using namespace std;
double f(double x)
{
    return exp(x)-sin(x)-7*cos(x);
    //can be the analytical expression of any
    //unimodal function
}
void Input(double& A, double& B, double&
teta, double& eps)
{
    cout << "A="; cin >> A;

```

```

cout << "B="; cin >> B;
cout << "teta="; cin >> teta;
cout << "eps="; cin >> eps;
}
void Optimization(double A, double B, double
teta, double eps, int& k, double a[100], double
b[100], double alfa[100], double beta[100],
double& xmin, double& fmin)
{
k=1;
a[1]=A;
b[1]=B;
alfa[1]=teta*a[1]+(1-teta)*b[1];
beta[1]=(1-teta)*a[1]+teta*b[1];
while (b[k]-a[k] > eps)
{
if (f(alfa[k]) < f(beta[k]))
{
a[k+1]=a[k];
b[k+1]=beta[k];
alfa[k+1]=teta*a[k+1]+(1-teta)*b[k+1];
beta[k+1]= (1-teta)*a[k+1]+teta*b[k+1];
}
else
{
a[k+1]=alfa[k];
b[k+1]=b[k];
alfa[k+1]= teta*a[k+1]+(1-teta)*b[k+1];
beta[k+1]=(1-teta)*a[k+1]+teta*b[k+1];
}
k=k+1;
}
xmin=(a[k]+b[k])/2;
fmin=f(xmin);
}

```

```

void Output(int k, double a[100], double b[100],
double alfa[100], double beta[100], double xmin,
double fmin)
{
int i;
cout.precision(8);
cout<<"The approximation value of the
minimum point is xmin="<<xmin<<endl;
cout<<"The minimum approximate value of
the function is fmin="<<fmin<<endl;
cout<<"The number of iterations performed
is k="<<k<<endl;
cout<<"i a[i] b[i] alfa[i] beta[i]
f(alfa[i]) f(beta[i]) b[i]-a[i]"<<endl;
for(i=1; i<=k; i++)
cout<<i<<" "<<a[i]<<" "<<b[i]<<"
"<< alfa[i]<<" "<<beta[i]<<" "<<
f(alfa[i])<<" "<< f(beta[i])<<" "<<
b[i]-a[i]<<endl;
}
int main()
{
int k;
double A, B, teta, eps, a[100], b[100], alfa[100],
beta[100], xmin, fmin;
Input(A, B, teta, eps);
Optimization(A, B, teta, eps, k, a, b, alfa, beta,
xmin, fmin);
Output(k, a, b, alfa, beta, xmin, fmin);
return 0;
}

```

In what follows, we will perform some numerical experiments, for various values of the parameter θ , considering the values of the other input parameters as fixed. The intermediate values will also be tabulated. For $\theta = 0.618033$ (the last

line in Table 1) we obtain the results for golden section method.

Table 1. Output Data for Different Values of the Parameter θ

A	B	$f(x)$	θ	ϵ	x_{min}	f_{min}	k
-8	-3	$e^x - \sin(x) - 7 * \cos(x)$	0.500001	0.00001	-6.1415952	-7.068916	20
-8	-3	$e^x - \sin(x) - 7 * \cos(x)$	0.51	0.00001	-6.14159	-7.068916	21
-8	-3	$e^x - \sin(x) - 7 * \cos(x)$	0.52	0.00001	-6.141595	-7.068916	22
-8	-3	$e^x - \sin(x) - 7 * \cos(x)$	0.53	0.00001	-6.1415898	-7.068916	22
-8	-3	$e^x - \sin(x) - 7 * \cos(x)$	0.618033	0.00001	-6.141591	-7.068916	29

Table 2. Intermediate Values for $\theta = 0.500001$

i	a[i]	b[i]	alfa[i]	beta[i]	f(alfa[i])	f(beta[i])	b[i]-a[i]
1	-8	-3	-5.500005	-5.499995	-5.6621631	-5.6621208	5
2	-8	-5.499995	-6.75	-6.749995	-5.7998295	-5.7998497	2.500005
3	-6.75	-5.499995	-6.1249988	-6.1249962	-7.0679422	-7.0679419	1.250005
4	-6.75	-6.1249962	-6.4374988	-6.4374975	-6.7615189	-6.7615215	0.62500375
5	-6.4374988	-6.1249962	-6.2812478	-6.2812472	-7.0000533	-7.0000539	0.3125025
6	-6.2812478	-6.1249962	-6.2031222	-6.2031219	-7.0555311	-7.0555313	0.15625156
7	-6.2031222	-6.1249962	-6.1640593	-6.1640591	-7.0671309	-7.067131	0.078125938
8	-6.1640593	-6.1249962	-6.1445278	-6.1445277	-7.0688855	-7.0688855	0.039063047
9	-6.1445278	-6.1249962	-6.1347621	-6.134762	-7.068751	-7.068751	0.019531563
10	-6.1445278	-6.134762	-6.1396449	-6.1396449	-7.0689026	-7.0689026	0.0097658008
11	-6.1445278	-6.1396449	-6.1420864	-6.1420864	-7.0689151	-7.0689151	0.0048829102
12	-6.1420864	-6.1396449	-6.1408656	-6.1408656	-7.0689141	-7.0689141	0.00244146
13	-6.1420864	-6.1408656	-6.141476	-6.141476	-7.0689159	-7.0689159	0.0012207324
14	-6.1420864	-6.141476	-6.1417812	-6.1417812	-7.0689159	-7.0689159	0.00061036743
15	-6.1417812	-6.141476	-6.1416286	-6.1416286	-7.068916	-7.068916	0.00030518433
16	-6.1416286	-6.141476	-6.1415523	-6.1415523	-7.068916	-7.068916	0.00015259247
17	-6.1416286	-6.1415523	-6.1415904	-6.1415904	-7.068916	-7.068916	7.6296387e-05
18	-6.1416286	-6.1415904	-6.1416095	-6.1416095	-7.068916	-7.068916	3.814827e-05
19	-6.1416095	-6.1415904	-6.1416	-6.1416	-7.068916	-7.068916	1.9074173e-05
20	-6.1416	-6.1415904	-6.1415952	-6.1415952	-7.068916	-7.068916	9.5371056e-06

As can be seen from the results presented in Table 1, the proposed algorithm requires a smaller number of iterations for any chosen values of the parameter θ , than the number of iterations performed by applying the golden section method, at the same tolerance value. This fact is also justifiable from mathematical point of view, because the uncertainty interval is reduced from one iteration to another at a higher rate in the case of the parametric algorithm.

In order to make the software implementation more efficient in terms of memory space used and execution speed, we present a version of it that does not use arrays.

Program in C++

```
#include <iostream>
#include <math.h>
using namespace std;
double f(double x)
{
    return exp(x)-sin(x)-7*cos(x);
    //can be the analytical expression of any
    //unimodal function
}
void Input(double& A, double& B, double&
teta, double& eps)
{
```

```

cout << "A="; cin >> A;
cout << "B="; cin >> B;
cout << "teta="; cin >> teta;
cout << "eps="; cin >> eps;
}
void Optimization(double A, double B, double
teta, double eps, int& k, double& xmin, double&
fmin)
{
double a, b, alfa, beta;
k=1;
a=A;
b=B;
alfa=teta*a+(1-teta)*b;
beta=(1-teta)*a+teta*b;
while (b-a > eps)
{
if (f(alfa) < f(beta))
{
b=beta;
beta= (1-teta)*a+teta*b;
alfa=teta*a+(1-teta)*b;
}
else
{
a=alfa;
alfa= teta*a+(1-teta)*b;
beta=(1-teta)*a+teta*b;
}
k=k+1;
}
xmin=(a+b)/2;
fmin=f(xmin);
}
void Output(int k, double xmin, double fmin)

```

```

{
cout.precision(8);
cout<<"The approximation value of the
minimum point is xmin="<<xmin<<endl;
cout<<"The minimum approximate value of
the function is fmin="<<fmin<<endl;
cout<<"The number of iterations performed
is k="<<k<<endl;
}
int main()
{
int k;
double A, B, teta, eps, xmin, fmin;
Input(A, B, teta, eps);
Optimization(A, B, teta, eps, k, xmin, fmin);
Output(k, xmin, fmin);
return 0;
}

```

By running this version of the program for the input parameters given in Table 1, we obtain the same values of the output data, in a shorter time and with a substantial saving of memory space.

Conclusion

The current paper presents a parametric algorithm for finding the minimum of a unimodal function and establishes the advantages of its use. It is not necessary to know information about the derivative of the function to apply this algorithm. The method of golden section can be obtained from the proposed algorithm through a particular choice of the parameter. The software implementation of the algorithm was done in the C++ language, in a first version using vectors to directly illustrate the pseudocode, and in the second version using only simple variables to make the program more efficient in terms of the memory space used as well as execution speed. The results obtained in the numerical experiments for various values of

the parameter showed that it performs a smaller number of iterations than the golden section method, as the parameter tends to the value of 0.5 through higher values, this fact being also justifiable from theoretical point of view. These advantages of the algorithm and the implemented software make it applicable in optimization problems both in mathematics and in practical issues from applied sciences.

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Conflict of Interests

The author declare has no Conflict of interests / Competing interests to disclose.

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